

PRODUCTION, PROXIMATE COMPOSITION AND CONSUMER ACCEPTABILITY OF BISCUITS FROM WHEAT/SOYBEAN FLOUR BLENDS

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ABSTRACT

The use of wheat and soybean flour blends in the preparation of biscuits was studied. The flour blends of wheat (WF) and soybean (SF) were composite at replacement levels of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80% and 90%. The proximate composition of the various flour blends used for the preparation of biscuits were determined using standard methods. The biscuits produced were evaluated for their proximate composition and sensory attributes. From the results, the protein content of the blends increased steadily with increasing content of soybean flour (SF) (13.18% in 90:10, WF: SF to 27.44% in 10: 90, WF: SF) while carbohydrate decreased. Similarly, the protein content of the biscuits increased with increasing supplementation with soybean flour. The protein content of biscuits increased from 12.08% in 90:10, WF: SF to 25.48% in 10: 90, WF: SF samples. In the same way, the energy content of the biscuits increased as the level of soybean flour inclusion increased. The energy content of the biscuits increased from 375.6kcal in 90: 10, WF: SF to 435.5kcal in 10: 90, WF: SF. The results also showed that the biscuits fortified with 10% soybean flour was the most acceptable because there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) between this sample and the control (Biscuits made from 100% wheat flour). The other samples of biscuits were significantly different ($p<0.05$) from the control with the biscuits made from 100% soybean flour having the lowest score (4.8) in general acceptability.

KEYWORDS: Biscuits, proximate composition, acceptability, wheat-soybean flour blends.

INTRODUCTION

Biscuits are flour confections produced from dough or batter and baked to a very low moisture content within a short period of time to make them flaky and crispy. The consumption of biscuits and other western styled bakery products such as bread and cakes prepared from wheat flour has become very popular in Nigeria, especially, among children (Ayo and Nkama, 2003). The low protein content of wheat flour, which is the most important ingredient used for the production of different kinds of baked goods has been of major concern in its utilization.

The enrichment or fortification of biscuits and other bakery products with other protein sources such as oilseeds and legumes has received considerable attention. This is because oil seed and legume proteins are high in lysine, an essential limiting amino acid in most cereals (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985). Whole legumes contain relatively high amount of protein compared to other plant foodstuffs. Legume proteins should complement the protein in cereal grains since the chemical and nutritional characteristics of legumes make them natural complements to cereal-based diets (Altschull, 1974).

The soybean, (*Glycine max*) a grain legume, is one of the richest and cheapest sources of plant protein that can be used to improve the diet of millions of people, especially the poor and low income earners in

developing countries because it produces the greatest amount of protein used as food by man (LIU, 2000). Soybean can be processed into soymilk, soy sauce, tofu (soybean curd), soy-yoghurt, soy sprouts, soy flour and many other soy products. Defatted soybean flour can be used for the production of protein isolates and concentrates.

Fig 1: Flow Chart for The Production of Cooked full-fat Soybean flour.

Nutritionally, soybean protein resembles animal protein more closely than other vegetable proteins. Soybean protein constitutes about 40% of the total solids and plays a very important role in the enrichment of cereal-based baked goods (Fukushima, 1999). It is also a rich source of vitamin, minerals and is relatively low in crude fibre (Oyenuga, 1968). Soybean is one such protein sources, which when used partially to replace or complement wheat flour in the production of bakery products such as biscuits, bread and other confectionery could go a long way in improving the nutritional status of such products. The objective of the study was to determine the nutrient constituents and acceptability of biscuits prepared from wheat flour supplemented with soybean flour at different levels of substitution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Materials

Mature Soybean seeds (*Glycine max*) were bought from a local market in Owerri, Nigeria whereas the wheat flour and other ingredients used for this study were purchased at Ogbuke market, Elele, Nigeria. This research work was carried out in Department of Food Science and Technology, Madonna University, Elele, Rivers State, Nigeria. (June, 2006)

Preparation of Full-Fat Soybean Flour

The full-fat soybean flour was prepared according to the method described by Ihekoronye and Ngoddy (1985) as shown in Figure 1. During preparation, two kilograms of soybean seeds which were free from dirt and other foreign particles such as stones, sticks and leaves were weighed, cleaned and soaked in tap water for 8 hours. Thereafter, the seeds were drained, dehulled manually, boiled (100°C, 30min) and dried

in cabinet dryer (65⁰C, 6hr). During drying, the dehulled seeds were stirred at intervals of 30 minutes to ensure uniform drying. The dried seeds were milled (attrition mill) and sieved to obtain cooked full-fat soy bean flour. The full-fat soybean flour obtained was finally packaged in an air tight container due to the hygroscopic nature of soybean flour unit used for blending and analysis.

Flour Blending

Wheat flour (WF) was composite at 10, 20, 30 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90% levels with soybean flour (SF) on a replacement basis in Kenwood blender. The flour blends were individually packaged in sealed polyethylene bags and kept at room temperature until used for biscuit production and analysis. The various flour blends are shown in Table 1

Fig 2: Flow Chart for the Production of Biscuits

Preparation of Biscuits

The biscuits were prepared using the creaming method described by Okaka (1997) as shown in Figure 2. The basic formulation was 100% flour, 40% fat, 20% beaten egg, 60% sucrose, 4% milk, 2% salt and 1% baking powder. The 100% flour was systematically replaced for the wheat flour (WF) with 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90% soybean flour (SF)

During the biscuit making, the sugar and fat were initially creamed in a mixer (Model AT 220A) to produce a creamy mixture before the flour and other dry ingredients were added. Thereafter, the mixture was

Table 1: Flour Blends

Samples	WF (%)	SF (%)
A	100	0
B	90	10
C	80	20
D	70	30
E	60	40
F	50	50
G	40	60
H	30	70
I	20	80
J	10	90
K	0	100

thoroughly mixed to form hard consistent dough. The dough obtained was thoroughly kneaded manually on a smooth clean table for about 5 mins. The dough was thinly rolled on a wooden board with rolling pin to uniform thickness (2mm) and cut out (using biscuit cutter) to desired shapes of similar sizes. The cut out biscuit dough pieces were placed in a greased baking tray and baked in a hot oven (200⁰C) for 20 mins. The biscuits were cooled immediately after baking and packaged individually in an air tight container and kept at room temperature until used for analysis and sensory evaluation. Wheat biscuits were similarly baked/produced as reference.

Chemical Evaluation

Proximate analysis was carried out on each of the flour blends and the biscuits. All determinations were carried out in triplicates. Protein determination was by kjeldahl method (Pearson, 1973). Fat, ash and moisture content determination methods were as described by Pearson (1973). The carbohydrate was determined by difference (Bryant *et al*, 1988). Food energy was calculated using the Atwater factor 4 x protein, 4 x carbohydrate, 9 x fat (Marero *et al*, 1988).

Sensory Evaluation

The biscuits were evaluated by a panel of fifteen untrained judge drawn from the University Community for attributes of colour, texture, flavour and general acceptability on a hedonic scale of 1-9 where 1 = dislike extremely and 9 = like extremely (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy 1985).

Statistical Analysis

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in all the analysis for detection of significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among samples. The turkey test was used in separating significant means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate composition of the various flour blends are shown in Table 2. The moisture content ranged from 12.27% to 14.62%. The differences could be attributed to inadequate drying of soybean seeds after soaking and boiling. The wheat flour (WF) appeared to be better dried as reflected in the moisture content values for the flour.

The ash content of all the flour blends differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) from each other. The differences were observed because the ash content of the blends increased steadily with increasing content of soybean flour (SF). Legumes have been reported to be good sources of ash (Pyke, 1981). This addition effect was also observed for fat and protein. In other words, the ash, fat and protein contents of the blends increased as the level of soybean flour inclusion increased. However, the carbohydrate content of the WF/SF blends decreased with the increasing concentration of soybean flour (SF). The result showed that soybeans are not good sources of carbohydrate when compared to other legumes (Salunkhe *et al*, 1992).

Table 2: Means ^{1,2} of Proximate Composition of Wheat/Soybean flour blends on dry weight basis.

Samples	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Fat (%)	Nx5.75 Protein (%)	Carbohydrate (%)
A	12.27 ^a	0.86 ^a	0.82 ^a	11.62 ^a	73.43 ^a
B	12.42 ^a	1.88 ^b	3.22 ^b	13.18 ^b	69.30 ^b
C	12.64 ^a	2.08 ^c	4.68 ^b	14.46 ^{ab}	65.92 ^b
D	13.28 ^b	2.42 ^c	6.28 ^c	16.32 ^c	62.80 ^b
E	13.26 ^a	2.46 ^c	7.86 ^c	16.86 ^c	59.57 ^c
F	11.62 ^c	2.86 ^c	8.42 ^{ab}	17.44 ^d	60.66 ^c
G	12.82 ^a	3.18 ^d	9.64 ^d	19.22 ^{ac}	57.14 ^{ab}
H	12.22 ^a	3.32 ^d	12.18 ^e	22.82 ^e	51.66 ^{ac}
I	12.62 ^a	3.56 ^a	14.08 ^f	24.24 ^{de}	46.50 ^d
J	13.42 ^b	3.86 ^d	16.02 ^{ac}	27.44 ^f	42.85 ^{dc}
K	14.62 ^d	4.62 ^a	18.46 ^e	25.64 ^{fe}	34.86 ^e

¹ Means of triplicate samples

² Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$)

The supplementation of wheat flour (WF) with soybean flour (SF) produced the desired effect of increasing the protein content of the blends, which will in turn improve the nutritional quality of biscuits produced from these blends.

The proximate composition of biscuits made from WF/SF blends are shown in Table 3. The moisture content of all the biscuit samples was not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$). They were also similar with those reported by Akpapunam and Darbe (1994). The protein contents was significantly different ($P < 0.05$). The biscuits produced from blends with higher concentrations of soybean

flour contained more protein than the ones made from blends containing less proportion of soybean flour. There was a gradual decrease in the carbohydrate content of the biscuits from sample A to sample K. The ash content of all the samples was higher than those previously reported for biscuits. The fat content of the biscuit samples was similarly higher than those reported earlier for biscuits. The increase in fat content of all the biscuit samples could be attributed to the fact that the soybean flour was not defatted. However, soybeans have been reported to be good sources of fat (Iwe and Onuh, 1992).

The energy content of all the biscuit samples ranged from 366.28 kcal/ 100g to 435.48 kcal/100g. There was significant difference in the energy content of the biscuits ($p < 0.05$). The energy contents of the biscuit samples were higher than those reported by Oyewole *et al*, (1996). The increase in energy content of the biscuits resulted from the high protein, fat and carbohydrate contents of the blends used for their production.

Table 3: Means ^{1,2} of Proximate Composition of Biscuits Produced from WF, SF and WF:SF Blends

Samples	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Fat (%)	Nx5.75 Protein (%)	Carbohydrate (%)	Energy (Kcal/100g)
A	9.86 ^a	1.42 ^a	2.28 ^a	11.22 ^a	75.22 ^a	366.28 ^a
B	9.44 ^a	1.76 ^b	4.08 ^b	12.08 ^a	72.64 ^a	375.60 ^a
C	9.62 ^a	1.82 ^b	6.22 ^c	14.56 ^b	67.74 ^b	385.28 ^a
D	9.68 ^a	2.02 ^c	8.26 ^d	15.12 ^b	64.74 ^b	385.28 ^a
E	9.86 ^{aa}	2.12 ^c	9.82 ^c	16.64 ^c	62.17 ^c	401.14 ^c
F	9.48 ^a	2.18 ^c	11.32 ^{ab}	17.68 ^c	59.43 ^d	409.96 ^c
G	9.28 ^a	2.28 ^c	13.28 ^{ac}	18.08 ^{ab}	58.08 ^d	424.26 ^d
H	9.42 ^a	2.44 ^c	14.48 ^f	20.28 ^d	54.48 ^{ab}	428.96 ^d
I	9.62 ^a	3.62 ^d	16.22 ^{bc}	22.46 ^e	49.08 ^e	432.24 ^d
J	9.74 ^a	3.86 ^{ab}	16.88 ^{bc}	25.48 ^{de}	47.56 ^{ac}	435.48 ^e
K	9.36 ^a	3.74 ^d	17.22 ^{de}	24.28 ^{de}	44.58 ^{de}	432.22 ^e

¹ Means of triplicate samples

² Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$)

The scores of the flair sensory evaluation of the biscuits produced from wheat/soybean flour blends are shown in Table 4. The scores of various sensory attributes were low in all the biscuits samples from the different blends. In general, biscuits produced from 100% wheat flour (Sample A) used as control were better accepted by the judges and were not significantly different from each other. However, the unique baking property of wheat flour has been well known (Ihekoronye and Ngoddy, 1985). Wheat flour generally has a better baking quality than any other type of flour. The substitution of wheat flour (WF) with soybean flour (SF) in all the biscuit samples up to 60% produced good results. Beyond this level, the sensory scores were very poor on the average. Acceptable results were also reported for African bread fruit kernel / wheat flour blended biscuits (Akubor *et al*, 2000).

CONCLUSION

Biscuits of acceptable quality similar to those made from wheat flour were produced from WF/SF blends. Substitution of wheat flour (WF) with soybean flour (SF) beyond 60% did not produce good results.

Therefore, substitution beyond this level is not encouraged. From the study, it was observed that the biscuits produced had better nutritional quality than those produced from 100% wheat flour because of their high protein content despite the high level of sugar (Sucrose) used for the production of biscuits which may impair protein availability due to the incidence of maillard or carbonyl amine reaction. Also, further studies

should be performed on wheat flour/soybean blended biscuits to evaluate their respective protein quality and availability.

The enhancement of the nutritional value of biscuits with the addition of soybean flour, could help to alleviate the problem of protein – energy malnutrition prevalent in Nigeria and other developing countries of the tropics

Table 4: Means ^{1,2} of Sensory evaluation of Biscuits Produced from WF, SF and WF:SF Blends.

Sample	Colour	Texture	Flavour	General Acceptability
A	4.8 ^c	6.4 ^a	7.2 ^c	7.8 ^a
B	5.9 ^b	6.1 ^a	6.7 ^a	7.4 ^a
C	6.4 ^a	5.8 ^b	6.4 ^a	6.6 ^b
D	5.2 ^b	6.2 ^a	6.3 ^a	6.4 ^b
E	5.6 ^b	5.6 ^b	5.8 ^b	6.2 ^b
F	6.0 ^a	5.4 ^b	5.6 ^b	5.7 ^c
G	5.4 ^b	4.5 ^c	5.4 ^b	5.6 ^c
H	5.6 ^a	4.2 ^c	4.8 ^c	5.8 ^c
I	5.8 ^b	4.6 ^c	4.6 ^c	5.6 ^c
J	6.2 ^a	5.2 ^{ab}	4.4 ^c	5.4 ^c
K	6.8 ^a	4.7 ^c	4.2 ^c	4.8 ^d

¹ Means of 15 untrained Panelists / Judges

² Means in the same column and followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other (P>0.05)

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Okoye, J.I *et al*: Continental J. Food Science and Technology 2: 6 - 13, 2008

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